

Clinical Manifestations and Characterization of COVID-19

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Abstract

Given the relative novelty of COVID-19, much is still undetermined about its effects on different organ systems and the resultant effects on mortality. Although coronavirus primarily manifests as an acute respiratory disease, it can involve other organs, including the kidneys, heart, eyes, ear, nose, throat, skin, gastrointestinal tract, blood, and central nervous system (CNS). Coronavirus penetrates CNS via nerve cells, and it makes damage to the respiratory center, confusion, lethargy, disorientation, loss of senses of smell and taste in most cases, and other manifestations pertinent to brain impairments. Diagnosis of different manifestations of COVID-19 could be crucial as this could help clinicians and researchers better understand the virulence, pathology, and immune responses associated with SARS-CoV-2, and also early diagnosis of the disease in suspected cases leading to the development of effective therapies and treatment plans. Therefore, in this review, we aimed to concisely summarize the different effects of COVID-19, thus emphasizing that the disease can present in various manifestations and the healthcare providers need to be extra vigilant, approaching all cases with a high index of suspicion.

Keywords: COVID-19, clinical manifestations, diagnosis, SARS-CoV-2.

Introduction

Since December 2019, COVID-19 has been a global health issue. The main clinical presentations of this disease is a flu-like disease; however, cases with different clinical manifestations have also been reported in previous studies. Given the relative novelty of COVID-19, much is still undetermined about its effects on different organ systems and the resultant effects on mortality (1). Although coronavirus primarily manifests as an acute respiratory disease, it can involve other organs, including the kidneys, heart, eyes, ear, nose, throat, skin, gastrointestinal tract, blood, and central nervous system (CNS). Coronavirus penetrates CNS via nerve cells, and it makes damage to the respiratory center, confusion, lethargy, disorientation, loss of senses of smell and taste in most cases, and other manifestations pertinent to brain impairments (2). Diagnosis of different manifestations of COVID-19 could be crucial as this could help clinicians and researchers better understand the virulence, pathology, and immune responses associated with SARS-CoV-2, and also early diagnosis of the disease in suspected cases leading to the development of effective therapies and treatment plans. Therefore, in this review, we aimed to concisely summarize the different effects of COVID-19, thus emphasizing that the disease can present in various manifestations and the healthcare providers need to be extra vigilant, approaching all cases with a high index of suspicion.

Renal Manifestations of COVID-19

Although coronavirus primarily manifests as an acute respiratory disease, it can involve other organs, including the kidneys, heart, eyes, ear, nose, throat, skin, gastrointestinal tract, blood, and central nervous system (CNS). Coronavirus penetrates CNS via nerve cells, and it makes damage to the respiratory center, confusion, lethargy, disorientation, loss of senses of smell and taste in most cases, and other manifestations pertinent to brain impairments (3). Coronavirus in the kidney can make AKI and other impairments in kidney activity. AKI is a disease which blood urea and creatinine concentrations increase by the retention of nitrogenous wastes, decrease GFR, as well as extracellular fluid volume and electrolyte homeostasis derangement. Although AKI is an uncommon manifestation of SARS-CoV-2, it seems to be a fatal complication with early studies showing 3–9% prevalence of AKI in the cases with COVID-19 (2, 4). However, subsequent investigations revealed that AKI incidence in hospitalized cases with COVID-19 is from 5% to 23%, and recent cohort investigations have even shown an incidence of up to 46% which has increased to 68% in ICU cases. Some risk

factors are known for AKI in COVID-19 including the need for mechanical ventilation, intubation, old age, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, severe illness, obesity, male gender, and chronic renal failure. However, some investigations revealed that the cases with COVID-19, in addition to AKI, also develop the glomerular disease because hematuria and proteinuria have also been identified in these patients. The exact COVID-19 mechanism on kidney is not yet determined, but investigators propose that SARS-CoV-2 directly and indirectly involves the kidney (5). Since SARS-CoV-2 is detected in the urine, kidney damage pattern caused by the virus is limited to regions with ACE2 receptor, and the time course in which the virus found in the urine coincides with the initiation of AKI, so it was postulated that the virus directly involves the kidneys. The virus seems to enter the kidney cell by binding to membrane-bound ACE2 receptors in the glomerular podocyte cells and the apical membrane of proximal tubule cells, and in addition to involving the kidney epithelial cells, it affects the balance of renin-angiotensin system. The angiotensinogen is primarily converted to angiotensin-I by renin and then to angiotensin-II under the effect of angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE). Furthermore, angiotensin-II is converted to angiotensin 1–7 by the ACE2 which dilates blood vessels (6). If SARS-CoV-2 occupies ACE2, angiotensin-II levels increase, causing vasoconstriction, glomerular impairment, inflammation, and fibrosis. Recently it has been shown that SARS-CoV-2 also attacks host cells via CD 147-spike protein mechanism and this glycoprotein is highly synthesized in proximal tubule. Furthermore, SARS-CoV-2 makes kidney damage by activating inflammatory mechanisms and cytokine storm, initiating coagulation mechanisms, involving renal vascular endothelium, sepsis, hemodynamic instability as well as hypoxemia. Viral infection of endothelium by immune cell recruitment makes defective endothelial function and decreases the synthesis of vasodilators, including the nitric oxide. Reduced vasodilators increase the response to vasoconstrictors and, together with ischemia-induced oxidative stress resulting in AKI development (6, 7). Moreover, there are different suggestions about the timing of the initiation of AKI manifestations in different investigations. In an investigation performed on 66 cases with COVID-19, three patients had AKI manifestations, all of which became apparent in the severe cases after the first week of hospitalization. Other investigations have also shown the initiation of AKI manifestations from days 5–9 after the hospitalization. However, in one study, manifestations were initiated on the second day of hospitalization, and in four other investigations, there were manifestations at the time of admission (5, 6).

COVID-19 Induced Kidney Dysfunction and Mortality

Given the relative novelty of COVID-19, much is still undetermined about its effects on different organ systems and the resultant effects on mortality. Current research proposes that renal damages in COVID-19 is related to increased rate of mortality. A retrospective study of 372 cases hospitalized in the ICU with COVID-19 was performed to assess the effects of kidney injury on final outcomes. Kidney injury was diagnosed according to the Kidney Disease: Improving Global Outcomes (KDIGO) criteria (8). Cases were divided into five groups: those with no kidney injury; those who had new-onset AKI; those with pre-existing CKD; those with ESRD; and those who had previous surgery of renal transplantation. In-hospital mortality was assessed as the primary outcome, while change in mean creatinine and need for RRT were evaluated as secondary outcomes. Of the 372 cases, 168 (45%) developed AKI during their ICU stay (4, 8). Forty-eight cases (13%) had preexisting renal damage. This study showed that COVID-19 cases with AKI or CKD have greater in-hospital mortality than those with preserved renal activity. Of the 216 cases, 107 with AKI and/or CKD (50%) died in hospital compared to only 32/156 (21%) in the non-AKI group. Mortality rates were comparable when comparing cases with new-onset AKI to cases with pre-existing CKD. The highest mortality was reported in cases who had previously undergone renal transplantation. Worsening renal activity, as shown by increased KDIGO stage, was correlated with increased mortality. Moreover, of those who survived, a significant rate needed RRT after discharge. Though limited, these findings serve to indicate the considerable effects of kidney injury in COVID-19 results. More studies are required to refine treatment to prevent kidney impairment, thereby improving patient mortality (4, 7).

Treatment of COVID-19-Related Kidney Injury

Kidney involvement in COVID-19 is prevalent and clinical manifestations can range from mild proteinuria to progressive AKI, necessitating RRT. Given the considerable kidney involvement in the disease presentation of COVID-19 and findings linking kidney activity decline to mortality, treatment of COVID-19-related kidney impairment is a vital area that requires to be assessed more. In a multicenter, retrospective, observational investigation, it has been shown through a univariate Cox regression of 193 COVID-19 cases that proteinuria, hematuria, and increased blood urea nitrogen levels, serum creatinine, uric acid as well as D-dimer were significantly correlated with the death of COVID-19 cases (9, 10). Their findings also proposed that COVID-19 cases who developed AKI had approximately 5.3 times mortality risk than cases without AKI. The fatality in these disorders should prompt practitioner to employ a high degree of consideration in the assessment of kidney activities of cases with severe COVID-19

affliction, regardless of their previous status of the disease. Moreover, practitioner should assess any potential treatments to protect kidney activities at the early stage of the disease and renal replacement treatments in severely ill cases particularly those with strong inflammatory reactions or a cytokine storm (10, 11). Currently, there is no effective treatment for COVID-19 induced AKI, and treatment of COVID-19 related AKI is commonly similar to cases with AKI related with other etiologies such as sepsis. Current treatment of COVID-19 related AKI includes supportive management, avoiding nephrotoxic medications, and, if possible, an early application of RRT. Implementation of the KDIGO supportive care recommendations (e.g., avoidance of nephrotoxins, common evaluation of serum creatinine and urine output, hemodynamic assessment) in critically ill cases with kidney involvement is likely to decrease both occurrence and severity of AKI in COVID-19, but needs validation. Evidence shows that conservative treatment of volume overload, metabolic acidosis, and hyperkalemia can be attempted before implementing kidney replacement therapy (KRT). In a study, methods were described for potentially delaying KRT to conserve important resources during hospital surges, including escalating dosages of IV loop diuretics in cases with volume overload, IV sodium bicarbonate solution in cases with severe metabolic acidosis, and use of rapid-acting potassium binders such as sodium zirconium cyclosilicate for hyperkalemia. Accurate fluid therapy is crucial to be used as a method to decrease the risk of noncardiogenic pulmonary edema, usual related with ARDS (11-13). In the absence of shock and hypotension, fluid conservative treatment is suggested to make a negative fluid balance of 0.5e1.0 L per day. Techniques for adjusting fluid balance according to volume responsiveness and tolerance evaluation aim to restore normal volume condition and prevent volume overload, to decrease the risk of pulmonary edema, right ventricular overload, congestions, and subsequent AKI (12). It is critical to consider that cases admitted with COVID-19 can be often admitted with volume depletion due to pyrogenic effects and GI disorders, and pre-hospital fluid resuscitation is rarely carried out. These patients warrant the correction of hypovolemia to prevent AKI. In the presence of shock, fluid balance may be provided with RRT, especially if there is related AKI and oliguria. SARS, MERS, and sepsis have been successfully managed in the past with continuous renal replacement therapy (CRRT), as CRRT by hemofiltration and hemodiafiltration can have a role in the treatment of organ failure in these patients (11, 13). Therefore, CRRT may be effective in cases with COVID-19 and sepsis condition, but it requires to be more investigated exactly with respect to the logistical restrictions during the current pandemic. Unfortunately, well-established RRT treatments have struggled due to a lack of machines, supplies, and interventionists. The COVID-19 Treatment Guidelines Panel

suggests CRRT, if available, for critically ill cases who have AKI and develop indications for RRT. Assume CRRT is either not available or not possible due to a lack of resources, including equipment and personnel. In that case, the Panel suggests prolonged intermittent renal replacement therapy (PIRRT) rather than intermittent hemodialysis (IHD) (14, 15). The limitation of resources has necessitated novel substitutions to RRT approaches, including “sharing” CRRT machines between cases with each case receiving a daily 10e12 h session and utilizing peritoneal dialysis delivery not commonly used in North American ICUs for management of AKI. Beyond the selection of RRT methods, the dialysis prescription in COVID-19- related AKI shows significant considerations, and the ideal ultrafiltration target also remains undetermined. Hypoxemic respiratory failure and ARDS, both cardinal characteristics of severe COVID-19 patients, can be exacerbated by a fluid accumulation that is subsequently worsened by AKI. The decision to remove fluid via ultrafiltration and how fast to do so is still unknown as it may manifest with a trade-off in complications. For example, rapid fluid removal may improve oxygenation and improve removal of mechanical ventilation, but this ultrafiltration may, in turn, predispose cases to hypotension and secondary organ impairments. Moreover, RRT has been shown with obstacles associated with a state of hypercoagulability in severe COVID-19 patients that causes intra- and extracorporeal clotting problems with subsequent early termination of therapy (14, 16). Termination can decrease the gross quality of dialysis, metabolic imbalances, fluid overload enhanced blood loss due to more prevalent alterations in the system and is likely to promote more complications for cases. Therefore, specialists have reported the urgent require to establish specific anticoagulation regimens in cases with COVID-19 needing RRT. Recent studies have recommended the use of continuous veno-venous hemodialysis or continuous veno-venous hemodialysis filtration to reduce filtration fraction and decrease the risk of circuit clotting if using CRRT. Given that the optimal method for COVID-19-related kidney impairment management is still unknown, decisions for RRT modalities and treatments remain largely dependent on clinical judgment and resources available. One avenue that can be assessed for tailoring clinical practitioners specific to cases includes the use of kidney biopsies, which would improve understand the histological pattern of impairment (tubular, glomerular, and vascular) and the pathogenesis that could cause AKI (14-16). In a case report of granulomatous interstitial nephritis, a SARS-CoV-2-positive case with severe ARDS and multi-organ failure was reported, who showed oliguric AKI needing analysis. Given the broad differential diagnoses for AKI, they used a kidney biopsy that ultimately guided their treatment approach. Based on results, the decision was made to adjust treatments and initiate corticosteroids, and his individually tailored clinical treatment

plan led to recovery, discharge from rehabilitation, and no longer needed dialysis. This case shows the important value of kidney biopsies in clinical diagnoses and may affect patient outcomes if a treatable cause is detected. They also showed the more common recognized drug interactions in COVID-19 that can potentially be reversible, given the correct histopathology is shown (3). Unfortunately, various factors specific to COVID-19 including the respiratory and hemodynamic instability of AKI cases, anticoagulation that increases the risk of bleeding, and use of mechanical ventilation make obtaining kidney biopsies of suspected AKI cases very difficult. Moreover, the risk of exposure to hospital staff has severely limited the nonessential interventions carried out in infected cases. The use and criteria for warranted kidney biopsies are a critical area that requires to be more investigated and can potentially be suggestive in developing targeted biomarker treatments (17, 18).

Clinical Characteristics of Gastrointestinal Involvement

Different studies have shown that COVID-19 may be correlated with diverse GI symptoms, most frequently diarrhea, nausea/ vomiting, and abdominal pain. In a line with previous studies, a previous meta-analysis involving 10,890 cases found the prevalence of the GI symptoms as 7.7, 7.8, and 2.7% for diarrhea, nausea and/or vomiting, and abdominal pain, respectively. As firstly showed in a case from the USA, where the presented case had vomiting and diarrhea for 2 days before hospitalization, the cases infrequently show solitary GI manifestations without accompanying respiratory complaints (19, 20). Another investigation showed the prevalence of the GI manifestations to be 10–21%, and these manifestations mostly consisted of nausea/vomiting, diarrhea, and loss of appetite. Moreover, among all cases, about 10% showed the GI manifestations without concomitant respiratory symptoms. In a similar way, a large-scale investigation reported that 16% (183/1,141) of the cases suffering from COVID-19 had solely GI characteristics at initial presentation. Furthermore, the cases showing solely with the GI manifestations tend to be diagnosed late, which may facilitate viral dissemination among subjects with whom they have a close contact. This situation needs awareness among practitioner since these cases can be hospitalized for their GI manifestations in a non-COVID-19 inpatient unit, and this could arise a potential risk for dissemination. In another meta-analysis, the rate of diarrhea was in the range of 4.3–12.2%, while the rate of nausea/vomiting was between 2.6 and 8.0%. SARS-CoV-2 RNA on feces was assessed in 8 of 29 investigations included, and viral RNA positivity rate was 40.5% (19, 20). In parallel with these results, among 9 of 17 cases (52.9%) with detectable viral RNA in respiratory samples, fecal RNA positivity was approved by polymerase chain reaction (PCR) analysis up to 11 days of initial

manifestation. However, titers of viral RNA in fecal materials were significantly lower when compared to respiratory samples. Similarly, in a study, it has been shown that 11 out of 66 cases (16.7%) who recovered with COVID-19 therapy still carried viral genomic RNA in their stools for a median 11 days after initiation of signs. Moreover, fecal PCR test identified SARS-CoV-2 positivity in 23.3% of the cases, despite respiratory samples of these cases did not harbor any viral genomic material (20, 21). It is also important to consider that the interrelation between viral RNA positivity in stool and GI symptoms was shown quite heterogeneous in different investigations. Some investigations showed that the GI manifestations particularly diarrhea had a close association with higher probability of viral RNA carriage in fecal samples, higher SARS-CoV-2 viral load, and longer duration of fecal viral shedding. On the contrary, in another investigation, the presence of the GI symptoms was claimed not to be correlated with viral RNA positivity in stool. Moreover, the disease severity did not parallel with prolonged duration of viral shedding in stool. In contrast to cases without the GI manifestations, those with the GI complaints are more prone to cough, fatigue, and headache. Common laboratory assessments show higher levels of neutrophils and acute phase reactants, like C-reactive protein (CRP) among cases with the GI manifestations, proposing that systemic inflammation occurs more severely in these cases. Moreover, abnormalities of liver function assessments were seen in up to 17.5% of the cases with the GI manifestations compared with 8.8% of the cases without the GI manifestations. The prevalence of ARDS was significantly higher in the cases with the GI manifestations (6.7%) compared with those not having any GI manifestation (2.08%) (19, 21). Consistently, the rates of recovery and hospital discharge were considerably higher in those without the GI manifestations than in the cases having the GI manifestations. In contrast, according to another study, only abdominal pain was a predictor of severe COVID-19 and death. In this investigation, it was clearly noted that neither nausea/vomiting nor diarrhea were harbingers of more severe disease. This can be clarified by possible correlation with secondary involvement of the digestive tract through dysregulated inflammatory response developing in severe patients. Among cases with COVID-19, diarrhea is commonly mild and known by loose to watery stools that are not bloody. Its recovery commonly takes more than a median of 5 days. Endoscopy is performed on such a case usually does not approve major mucosal changes, but microscopic assessment identified infiltration of large numbers of lymphocytes into the lamina propria. These results are similar to what we are used to see in viral gastroenteritis (19, 20).

Pharmacologic Management of GI Manifestations in COVID-19

Microecological preparation

The intestinal flora produces different vitamins, bile acids, immune factors, and fatty acids *via* the decomposition of food and has a role in immune system regulation. If there is impairment or damage in the intestinal flora and/or mucosa, the virus may more stimulate infection through this mechanism. Other investigations have shown that probiotics have the availability to treat diarrhea caused by rotavirus (22). Moreover, lactic acid bacteria and Bifidobacteria can contribute to antiviral antibodies in the human body, improving virus removal. Therefore, probiotic therapies and/or antiviral medications, and antibacterial medications may increase the manifestations of SARS-CoV-2 diarrhea. Regarding the diagnosis and treatment guidelines of COVID-19 in China, the use of intestinal flora modulators is suggested to preserve the intestinal micro-environmental balance and avoid secondary bacterial infection (22-24).

ACE2 inhibitors

As previously reported, ACE2 binds SARS-CoV-2 in cells. Therefore, to prevent SARS-CoV-2 infection the interaction between the receptor connection domain (RBD) of the virus and ACE2 could be blocked. A number of investigations have reported that ACE2 inhibitors can modulate bowel metabolism, innate immunity, production of antibacterial peptides, and intestinal microbial homeostasis. It was experimentally approved that the ACE2 mechanism in epithelial cells of the small intestine stimulate mTOR by nutrient stimulation and/or the tryptophan-nicotinamide mechanism, thus regulating the composition of intestinal flora, and reducing GIT indications in mice (24). Azathioprine is an immunosuppressive medication similar to chloroquine. A recent investigation assessed azathioprine and showed that it could be modulated as an ACE2 inhibitor. Furthermore, *in vitro* investigations have reported that Vaccinia virus can be prevented by azathioprine. With regard to molecular mechanism, azathioprine competitively binds to ACE2, using a single chain (ScFv) antibody fragment attached to ACE2 or SARS-CoV-2, *via* the RBD. Therefore, the human recombinant ACE2 antibody Fc segment bound by the S protein plays its role by inhibiting attachment of the virus to ACE2. It has been reported that a combination of Chinese agents and ACE2 provided the prevention of SARS CoV-2 infection (24, 25).

Diet and Enteral Nutrition

A number of COVID-19 cases have significant anorexia. To ensure effective treatment, the basic energy, absorption, enteral and peristalsis movement of the intestine, and normal activity of GIT micro-organisms and mucosal immunity should be considered as well as the functioning

of the GIT and patients' nutrition. Nutritional risk evaluation should be carried out in cases with serious COVID-19 and gastrointestinal manifestations (26). Once the risk of enteral nutrition has been removed, enteral nutrition should immediately be restored. If the patient has a gastrointestinal problem and cannot withstand enteral nutrition, parenteral nutrition should be performed with a sufficient supply of energy. Cases in poor condition can be given digestive enzymes. A nasogastric tube can be applied for enteral feeding in cases who have undergone mechanical ventilation and cannot take food orally. A nasal jejunal tube can be put when cases are at high risk of reflux aspiration or cannot handle nasogastric tube feeding. Commonly, the patient gastrointestinal tolerability should be estimated exactly and the enteral nutrition program correspondingly modulated (24, 26).

Neurological Manifestations of COVID-19

There is strong evidence that SARS-CoV-2 infection in brain can cause several neurological problems and changes ranging from nonspecific to moderate to severe disorders (27, 28). Systemic neurological and nonspecific manifestations include headache, dizziness, fatigue and myalgia that range from 30 to 45% in COVID-19 cases. Moderate manifestations include anosmia or hyposmia, disturbance in taste, smell and visual dysfunctioning. Paralysis, epilepsy and consciousness problems have also been shown. Severe manifestations include cerebrovascular problems such as intracerebral hemorrhage, cerebral venous thrombosis and ischemic stroke (29, 30). While long term consequence of infection can result in demyelinating and neurodegenerative problems. Therefore, the explanation of neuroinvasive pathways and related interactions is critical to clarify the potential pathological consequences and to design new pharmacological treatments and diagnostic methods for the treatment of COVID-19. Neurological disorders of COVID-19 seems to be both diverse and uncommon in behavior. The neurological symptoms may be the consequence of metabolic abnormalities triggered by the infection, autoimmune response against virus or result of direct effect of the virus on central or peripheral nervous system. In following subsections, we provide brief explanation of some of the critical neurological symptoms related to COVID-19 (28-30).

Anosmia and Ageusia

Loss of smell (anosmia) and loss of taste (ageusia) are common manifestations of COVID-19. Disturbance in olfactory and gustatory activity of COVID-19 cases are possibly due to the virus mediated impairment to the epithelial cells of the oral and nasal mucosa. A large number of ACE2 receptors are produced in nasopharynx, oral mucosa, and olfactory epithelial cells. When

the virus attaches to the ACE2 receptor in oral and nasal mucosa, it prevents the function of sensory receptor cells that participate in gustation and olfaction. It was shown that the SARS-CoV-2 penetrates along the olfactory bulb and eventually cause fast, transneuronal outspread of the virus to attached areas of the brain as well. Hence, the invasion and multiplication of SARS-CoV-2 at early stages of the infection cause impairment in the olfactory nerves and therefore, clarifies the mechanism behind anosmia (29, 30). While in the case of ageusia as well, ACE2 receptors appear in large number on the epithelial cells of the oral mucosa. When SARS-CoV-2 binds to the receptor on oral epithelial cells, it causes the dysfunction of oral cavity causing ageusia in the initial stages of the viral infection. An investigation of 68 COVID-19 cases revealed that abnormal taste and smell are resolutely correlated with COVID-19. In a European investigation of 417 cases, loss of smell was found in 86% of the COVID-19 cases while oral dysfunctioning was shown in 82% of the cases. However, a considerable variation is observed in COVID-19 cases of Asia and Europe in terms of taste and smell perception. An investigation in China showed that there were only 5% of the COVID-19 cases suffering from taste and smell disturbances. This is in contrast to the European investigation of COVID-19 cases where the frequency of olfactory and gustatory impairment was reported to be 33.9–88.0%. This inconsistency may be due to the ACE2 polymorphism or due to the heterogeneity in allele frequency of ACE2 receptor that causes variation in outcomes and manifestations of COVID-19. Taken together, anosmia and ageusia are the most common neurological manifestations of COVID-19 and the cases with these manifestations should be assessed for COVID-19 particularly during this pandemic (29, 31).

Encephalopathy

Brain encephalopathy is a pathobiological disorder which progresses from hours to days causing changed personality, cognition, consciousness (along with clinical presence of coma or delirium) and behavioral problems. In a retrospective investigation of 214 COVID-19 cases in China, 25% (53) of the cases had CNS related manifestations like dizziness in 17% (16) cases, disturbed consciousness in 7% (16) cases and headache in 13% (28). In another investigation of critical cases with COVID-19 infection, 84% had neurological manifestations that included encephalopathy and corticospinal related manifestations (31). Three more investigations of COVID-19 encephalopathy have been shown, one each from Iran, Iraq and the USA spanning within an age group from 30 to 75 years. In all the three cases cough and fever were the initial manifestations along with initiation of asthenia and confusion. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and computerized tomography (CT) scanning of brain were shown

to be unimportant. Though, in some countries electroencephalogram (EEG) was used for the approval of encephalopathy (29).

Infectious toxic encephalopathy

Infectious toxic encephalopathy, which is also known as acute toxic encephalitis, is a type of brain reversible dysfunction disorder that occurs due to factors like hypoxia, systemic toxemia and metabolic diseases during the course of acute infection. The main pathological changes include edema which upon CSF analysis revealed no evidence of inflammation. Cases with COVID-19 infection show different and complex range of manifestations. Initially mild manifestations may arise such as dysphoria, headache and delirium. In severe patients, cases may show loss of consciousness, disorientation, coma and paralysis. COVID-19 cases commonly show severe viremia and hypoxia that can more result in toxic encephalopathy (31). Moreover, 40% of the COVID-19 cases have brain dysfunction manifestations including edema in the brain tissues in severe conditions. Taken together, these investigations shown that COVID-19 may cause mild to severe infectious toxic encephalopathy. The communication between the nervous system and the immune system has an ancient evolutionary origin as it has been thought that every physiological action including immune reactions are under the control of brain. It is well known that immune system and neuronal system cross-talk and both have role in immune response. This signaling is carried out by different molecules such as opioid peptides like enkephalin and endorphins. These neuropeptides were originally identified in the CNS, and were later detected in immune cells and have immunomodulatory characteristics. Endorphins and enkephalins can have role in different immunological functions like antibody synthesis, lymphocyte proliferation, and natural killer cell mediated cytotoxicity. They are physiological modulators of the immunological response as well as act as humoral mediators between the immune system and the CNS (31, 32). They can have role as mediators and enhancers of the biological response. It has been shown that opioid peptides have role in immune regulation. Enkephalin can increase the secretion of pro-inflammatory mediators like interleukin (IL)-6. Furthermore, it affects the intracellular signal transduction in T-cells and has role in humoral immunity causing antibody synthesis. It has been shown that enkephalin triggers generation of B and T cell and can increase the number of T helper and T cytotoxic cells. The appearance of these opioid peptides mRNAs has been shown in different cells like the synthesis of enkephalin was detected in monocytes and T lymphocytes, in fetal thymocytes along with B and T lymphocytes. It has been recently revealed that they also have anti-inflammatory role as in the inflamed tissue, the delivery of endorphins via lymphocyte

trafficking system would increase the analgesic and anti-inflammatory characteristics. It has been shown that endorphins have protective role against neurotropic murine coronavirus, MHV-JHM (JHMOV). The virus can lead to paralytic-demyelinating disease and encephalitis in susceptible strains of rats and mice. A single dose of beta-endorphin reduced the occurrence of viral-stimulated paralytic-demyelinating disease by 40–50% followed by considerable decrease in viral replication in the brain. Therefore, it can be concluded from the discussion that endorphins and enkephalins could be effective in boosting immunity in COVID-19 as they possess immunomodulatory characteristics. However, more extensive investigations are required to be carried out for more understanding (31, 32).

Seizures

Seizures may occur as a consequence of acute systemic sickness, adverse effect of treatment or as a primary neurological pathology in COVID-19 cases and can cause a broad range of manifestations from subtle twitching, convulsive activity to lethargy. In severe subjects, untreated seizures can rapidly exacerbate towards the convulsive status epilepticus and more frequently non-convulsive status epilepticus that are associated with high morbidity and mortality. Seizures are usually infrequent neurological manifestation in COVID-19 cases (33). In a recent study, it has been shown that out of 214 critical COVID-19 cases, only one case was reported with acute symptomatic seizures. While in some of the investigations triggering of new onset seizures by COVID-19 infection was shown. Different investigations have shown seizures in children having COVID-19 infection. Consistent seizures with paroxysmal episodes were reported in 2 infants with virus on nasopharyngeal swab but no respiratory manifestations. In an investigation of 168 hospitalized children with COVID-19 infection, seizures were shown in 3% of the children in which one had preexisting febrile seizures and the other three had previous epilepsy (28, 32).

Guillain-Barre Syndrome

Guillain-Barre Syndrome (GBS) has been presented as an important parainfectious neurological sequelae of COVID-19. It arises when the immune system is disturbed and attacks its own nerves that exist in the exterior region of spinal cord or brain and injures myelin sheath. The disease is related to a state of acute flaccid paralysis that commonly shows progressive symmetric weakness. Commonly, GBS is stimulated by campylobacteriosis and viral infections like Epstein-Barr virus (EBV), human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) and Zika virus. As it is clear that COVID-19 infection has an effect over the nervous system and the co-existence of

GBS with SARS-CoV-2 is not rare as infection by other viruses have also been reported in the etiology of GBS (32, 33). The association of COVID-19 with GBS is a temporal correlation that reveals a post-infective immune-mediated mechanism. The reason behind this correlation is an autoimmune interplay in which antibodies are synthesized against the surface glycoprotein that shares molecular similarity with peripheral nerve parts causing neurological manifestations. There may be immune response related to injury in GBS cases having COVID-19 since after infection the concentration of inflammatory mediators like IL-6, activities of macrophages, T-lymphocytes and endothelial cells are enhanced leading to complement activation, coagulation, vascular leakage and eventually organ impairment. Recent investigations have reported involvement of other coronaviruses with neurological disorders such as in a retrospective investigation of MERS-CoV, a case was thought to have GBS was shown to be overlapping with Bickerstaff's encephalitis. GBS correlated with COVID-19 cases revealed normal MRI findings of the CNS but an increase in post-contrast has been shown in lumbar and cervical nerve roots. It commonly develops from several days to weeks of infection. Furthermore, spinal imaging showed abnormal characteristics in 40% cases such as myelopathy, root enhancement and leptomeningeal increase (28, 33). One more investigation was performed on 16 cases where COVID-19 was approved with RT-PCR while GBS was validated with clinical assessment such as muscle strength evaluation. They performed CSF analysis and neurophysiological evaluation, each of them showed abnormalities in line with GBS diagnosis criteria. Another study also showed a case having GBS related to COVID-19 showing manifestations of weakness and numbness in lower extremities for 2 days. Moreover, the progression of weakness to high fever and diarrhea was diagnosed. A team of practitioner in Italy conducted an investigation on five cases and found that the interval from the initiation of COVID-19 manifestations and the arousal of initial manifestations of GBS ranges from 5 to 10 days. They showed that cases develop lower-limb weakness paresthesia, facial diplegia along with flaccid tetraparesis and ataxia, as first manifestation of GBS related to COVID-19. Though no case in the investigation stated dysautonomic characteristics. MRI revealed enhanced signal alterations of the caudal nerve roots, facial nerve; CSF analysis showed a reduced white-cell count and anti-ganglioside antibodies; electrophysiological investigations findings revealed low amplitude of compound muscle action potential, progressive motor distal latencies and fibrillation potentials were seen during electromyography. Treatment of this correlation includes exchange of plasma, intravenous immunoglobulins, supportive care and regular assessment. Therefore, cases reporting GBS should be evaluated for COVID-19 for early assessment and treatment (28, 32, 33).

Psychiatric Manifestations of COVID-19

COVID-19 and Major Depression

Systemic and tissue immune response have a role in the pathophysiology of different neuropsychiatric diseases through changing neurochemical environment, synaptic transmission and plasticity, production and secretion of neurotrophic mediators, and neurogenesis. In this regard, the major depression disorder (MDD) is one of the most common neuropsychiatric diseases associated with inflammatory impairment of the brain. A large body of previous findings have associated depression manifestations to pro-inflammatory mediators and neuroglial failure (34, 35). This association particularly is used to subtypes of depression occurring in the elderly. Ageing significantly impacts the levels and the function of pro-inflammatory mediators in the CNS. Systemic infection can itself stimulate major depression in elderly cases, due to age dependent reduction of immune homeostasis. In particular elevated serum levels of interleukin-1 β directly associate with emergence of late life MDD. Consistently, an association has been seen between inflammatory mediators and some specific manifestations, for example, elevated levels of TNF- α and IL-2 correlate with apathy and motor inhibition, whereas IL-6 correlates with anhedonia and suicidality. The levels of mediators decrease when cases recover normal mood levels; conversely mediators remain increased in cases resistant to treatment. Patients with severe COVID-19 are almost invariably accompanied with excessive host immune response, commonly known by a massive increase in plasma levels of IL-6, which directly associates with an unfavourable outcome of the disease. At the same time abnormally high levels of IL-6 were identified in the cerebral spinal fluid of suicide attempters, of cases suffering from either depression or schizophrenia, of old depressed cases and of mothers with postpartum depression. Numerous studies approved that changes in IL-6 levels, both in plasma and in the brain, have a role in the emergence of depression, although other factors, environmental or genetic in nature, have a substantial contribution (34-36). In the CNS IL-6 is known as a pro-inflammatory cytokine, which increases production and secretion of more inflammatory mediators and acute phase proteins by astrocytes and microglia. Therefore, IL-6, together with TNF- α and IL-1 β , can be noted as one of the primary modulators of the immune response in the brain, while astrocytes and microglia are the major responders to IL-6, as well as prominent producers of IL-6 triggered by damage and pathogen related molecular patterns (including viruses and their components), neurotransmitters and pro-inflammatory messengers. Physiological plasma concentrations of IL-6 in adults range between 1–10 pg/ml whereas in a systemic inflammation is raises to several ng/ml; and even

higher levels were shown for COVID-19. Interestingly, elevated levels of IL-6 have been identified in the serum, in the cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) and in the postmortem prefrontal cortex of cases with suicidal ideation, with non-fatal suicide attempts or committed suicides. At the same time no direct association was shown between plasma and CSF levels of IL-6 in cases with suicide attempts, nor such association was found for scores of depression severity. The IL-6 concentrations in circulation also associated with suicide endophenotypic behaviours, such as personality trait disorders, aggressivity and impulsivity. This is in line with different results proving the role of mediators in modulating emotions and behaviours through interacting with specific brain regions and different neuronal mechanisms. COVID-19 pandemic caused significant alterations in lifestyle and interpersonal relationships condemning many to prolonged loneliness. These conditions of psychosocial stress can also have a crucial effect on the most fragile cases affecting their ability to control emotions. Reduced control over impulsivity and sensations of fear in combination with inflammatory challenges to the brain may increase the risk of suicide (34, 36, 37).

COVID-19 and Bipolar Disorder

Abnormal balance between the pro-inflammatory (IL-6 and TNF- α) and anti-inflammatory mediators in the CNS and in the plasma have been repeatedly seen in cases with BD approving the notion that neuroimmune response may be a prominent factor with a role in pathogenesis of this disease. In acute phases of BD either during manic or depressive episode, an activation of inflammatory mechanisms were found, which was noted by many, but not by all, a typical characteristic of the acute illness, rather than a persistent trait of the disorder. Several mediators, such as IL-1 β , TNF- α , IL-6, interferon- γ were shown to increase in circulation in acute phases of BD, with a parallel decrease in the anti-inflammatory factors IL-10 and transforming growth factor β -1, particularly in the manic phase (36, 37). Analysis of the presence of pro-inflammatory mediators in the CSF in BD cases showed contradictory findings. Somewhat high CSF levels of IL-8, monocyte chemoattractant protein 1(MCP-1 / CCL-2), and neurofilament light chain were found in BD cases, although these mediators did not associate with the outcome of the disease. A meta-analysis of CSF mediators content in BD cases showed elevated concentrations of IL-1 β , the IL-8 revealed statistically insignificant increase and no changes for IL-6 were found. The inconsistency between the concentrations of interleukins and chemokines in blood plasma and in the CSF is another conflicting issue. It is of course tempting to assume that this inconsistency is lost in COVID-19 since the overload of interleukins and chemokines, compromised BBB and activation of CNS resident and invading immune cells

develops the neuroinflammation and promotes a bidirectional flow of inflammatory mediators through a permeable barrier. Such a scenario, however, remains highly unknown and much more studies and analysis are required to show possible correlation of viral infection in general and COVID-19 in particular with BD (34, 37).

COVID-19 and Reactive Psychosis

A wide spectrum of immune system disorders as well as infections (together of course with genetic vulnerability, abnormalities in neurotransmission, stress and exposure to environmental risk factors such as childhood maltreatment) are known as potential pathogenetic factors of reactive psychosis. Increased inflammation in psychosis has been approved by meta-analyses indicating elevated levels of immune mediators and their receptors in chronic schizophrenia, as well as in drug-naïve cases in their first episode of psychosis (FEP) (38). A recent investigation aimed at evaluating pro-inflammatory immune mediators profile in FEP cases revealed an up-regulation of IL-6, TNF- α and IL-1 β , which was not shown in healthy siblings, proposing familiar vulnerability is not involved in producing the inflammatory-related psychotic mechanisms. In an attempt to find the risk of the emergence of psychosis in cases infected with SARS-COV-2, it should be noted that high concentrations of IL-6, associate with decreased hippocampal size in schizophrenic cases accounting, at least partially, for their cognitive deficits. Furthermore, increased levels of IL-6 were identified in CSF of schizophrenic cases. Even intriguing is the observation that high concentrations of IL-6 in adolescents associate positively with the occurrence of psychosis later in life (37, 38).

COVID-19 and Schizophrenia

Significant number of psychotic episodes in the aftermath of Spanish flu pandemic has shown the possibility of increasing incidence of schizophrenic disorders in cases infected with the COVID-19. High levels of coronavirus immunoreactivity in patients with recent initiation of psychotic episodes as well as the serious neuropsychiatric complications including auditory and visual hallucinations as well as severe delusions have been shown in COVID-19 cases (38). Although neurodevelopmental origins of schizophrenia are commonly accepted, other etiological factors such as direct effect of a viral neuroinfection or indirect effect of immune aberrations occurring in adult cases cannot be excluded. Schizophrenia is also known as a neurodegenerative disorder in adulthood, with neuronal shrinkage and loss, oligodendrocyte damage, changes in synaptic connectivity, all likely correlated with cognitive injuries.

Although there are no evidence directly linking COVID-19 with the risk of schizophrenia, common occurrence of psychotic episodes shows the need for more, more detailed studies (38).

Cardiac Manifestations of COVID-19

COVID-19 and Cardiac Involvement

Most common cardiac symptoms in symptomatic SARS-CoV-2 cases are arrhythmias with ventricular tachycardia/fibrillation, shock, acute myocardial injury, chest pain, and ST-depression on electrocardiogram (ECG). It has been shown that high prevalence of heart failure as an extrapulmonary symptom of infection and the prevalence was higher in non-survivors. It is still unknown if it is occurred by viral affliction of myocardium or as a result of cytokine storm and a rapid inflammatory reactions (39). There are patients with acute myocarditis developing before the pulmonary manifestations; thus ventricular tachyarrhythmias may become the first clinical symptom of COVID-19 infection and results in enhanced risk of sudden cardiac death. Survival of cardiac arrests of cases in Wuhan was poor. Restoration of spontaneous circulation (ROSC) among 136 cases was reported in 18 cases (13.2 %), while only 4 (2.9%) survived for at least one month and 1 was in a favorable neurological condition. The main cause of cardiac arrest was respiratory and at the initiation of resuscitation the most frequent rhythm was asystole, while pulseless electrical activity and shakable had the lowest rate. The early US findings reported after the outbreak in New York City provided initial data regarding 5700 cases hospitalized due to infection. 2634 cases had reached the outcome of death (21%) or discharge, 14.2% been treated invasively at the ICU and 12.2% needed use of mechanical ventilators. Among hospitalized cases the most frequent comorbidities were hypertension, obesity and diabetes. For comparison, American rate for hypertension is 33.2%, obesity 39.8% and diabetes 15%. Despite the early findings, year after global coronavirus outbreak there was also seen strong correlation between coexistence of cancers with cardiovascular disorders and high-risk of death due to COVID-19. Cases with cancers and cardiac disorders died more commonly in comparison with cancer or cardiovascular disease solely (39, 40).

Management Approach for Cases with COVID-19 Related Cardiovascular Involvement

Myocarditis is commonly proposed in cases with chest pain during or after an influenza-like syndrome, with alterations on electrocardiography or laboratory assessments proposing an acute coronary syndrome with wall motion abnormalities but without coronary artery disease on coronary angiography. Some studies of cases presenting cardiac manifestations in COVID-

19 infection, myocardial inflammation, necrosis and ventricular dysfunction and arrhythmia propose not only myocardial injury but also potentially viral myocarditis or stress cardiomyopathy (40, 41).

Furthermore, especially critically ill COVID-19 cases admitted to intensive care unit develop different arrhythmias like sinus bradycardia, and tachycardia, supraventricular tachycardia, atrial fibrillation, and also non-sustained ventricular tachycardia. COVID-19 cases may be tachycardic due to fever, pain, etc. These patients can also have rhythm abnormalities in the setting of prolonged QTc, and electrolyte disturbances, especially high risk cases such as those with pre-existing cardiovascular disease, cancer or combination of both. To date, there is few publications reporting cases with congenital heart defects (ACHD) facing COVID-19. Because there are no published report of cases with congenital heart defects, all the therapeutic interventions are adapted and based on treating congenital heart defects like any other cardiovascular disorder, particularly heart failure (41). Based on the ACHD Anatomical and Physiological Stage Classification from the latest American Guidelines, cases with complex congenital heart disease anatomical stage III or symptomatic stage B, C, or D could have high risk for complications associated with SARS-CoV-2 infection. These findings propose a high incidence of lethal cardiac disorders, arrhythmias, heart failure which are similar to a stress cardiomyopathy or cytokine-related myocardial impairment in progressive phases of COVID-19 with fulminant cytokine release. The terminal phase could potentially be avoided by anticytokine treatment such as corticosteroids and IL-6 blocker tocilizumab. Nevertheless, the effect of immunosuppression on the course of this disease is unknown. While *in vitro* findings proposes that immunosuppressive treatments may prevent viral replication, long-term such treatment like used for recipients of heart transplant (HT) increases susceptibility to infection. Among twenty-eight HT cases in New York, mycophenolate mofetil was discontinued in 70%, and 26% had a dose reduction of calcineurin inhibitor. Investigations are being made to develop a structured approach to care of COVID-19 positive cases with heart involvement. A classification of these cases in the early stage and algorithms of diagnostics could provide effective triage for the treatment of cases (39, 41).

Dermatological Manifestations of COVID-19

Pathophysiology

The presence of the angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2), which is the primary receptor for SARS-CoV-2 entering skin cells, may clarify some of the vascular skin lesions of COVID-

19 infection due to critical immune antiviral response. The virus can directly make cutaneous lesions or indirectly due to vascular injuries, such as imposed vasculitis and thrombotic vasculopathy. The former may occur through direct viral inoculation, viral reactivation from a distant region, or immunotherapy (27, 42, 43).

Morphology

Dermatological symptoms of COVID-19 are considerably more polymorphic than any viral infection so far. Maculopapular, vesicular, and urticarial lesions are the most frequent cutaneous eruptions, respectively. Several investigations have been performed to make consensus on categorizing COVID-19 skin manifestations as follows (42, 43).

Urticarial Rash

Before the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic, many viral and bacterial pathogens such as cytomegalovirus (CMV), herpes simplex virus (HSV), Epstein-Barr virus (EBV), and mycoplasma were common infectious stimulators of urticarial eruptions and angioedema. Itching is almost always found under these circumstances. This dermatological manifestations usually takes seven days to resolve during moderate to severe COVID-19 in approximately 20% of the cases. These lesions are commonly localized on the trunk and extremities, often with sacral sparing. As with other hypersensitivities and allergic dermatitis, low-dose oral corticosteroids, in addition to antihistamines, can provide effective amelioration (43, 44).

Erythematous/Maculopapular/Morbilliform Rash

Occurring in about 21.3% of the cases, these eruptions are sometimes pruritic and commonly appear on the trunk and extremities. They may be found at the same time or evolve from mild involvement to a more diffuse pattern. These lesions can occur by SARS-CoV-2 itself, or medications used to treat COVID-19 infection, are variably pruritic and can last up to one week. Topical glucocorticoids, and in more severe patients, systemic corticosteroids can provide an appropriate relief (42, 44).

Papulovesicular Exanthema

These lesions can differ from diffuse polymorphic eruptions to a localized monomorphic pattern, commonly on the chest, upper abdomen, or back. Affecting about 29.4% of the cases, their duration can range from a few days up to 2 weeks, and they mainly evolve in the context of moderate to severe COVID-19. These eruptions are also characterized as “varicella-like”

eruptions due to their morphology and common features similar to the varicella-zoster virus (VZV). However, as the VZV can also be superimposed on pre-existing COVID-19 conducting a Tzanck smear or PCR of the vesicle fluid may be effective in excluding herpesviruses as the inciting factor. The lesions are commonly non-pruritic, do not leave scars and are self-limiting. Some investigations have included Grover's disease in the category of papulovesicular eruptions correlated with COVID-19. It is thought that some papulovesicular eruptions of COVID-19 may be the “pseudo-herpetic” type of Grover's disease (44, 45).

Chilblain-Like Acral Pattern

These lesions are known as erythematous-violaceous patches or plaques commonly found on the feet, sometimes on the hands, and rarely on the auricular area. They may be presented with itching, pain, or a burning sensation. “COVID toes,” also known as pseudo-chilblain or pernio-like lesions, are vasculopathy rashes presented in acral areas and found in 63% of the cases. The eruptions commonly appear in mild or even asymptomatic cases of COVID-19 and more frequently in children and young adults. Enhanced interferon release due to the cytokine response, direct viral impairment of the endothelium, obliterative microangiopathy, and coagulopathy induced by ischemia can be the causative pathways. These lesions seem to subside spontaneously as well (42, 45).

Livedo Reticularis/Racemosa-Like Pattern

This skin injuries seems to be a cross-linked pattern along with bluish discoloration of the skin and can occur either as a typical livedo reticularis or livedo racemosa. May involves about 6% of the cases,²⁵ these lesions are first symmetrical and lace-like, induced by cutaneous vasoconstriction or vascular flow disturbances and disappearing by themselves. On the other hand, the latter commonly consisted of more oversized, more irregular, and asymmetrical lesions associated with focal blood flow disturbances and may be associated with severe coagulopathies. These eruptions are more frequent in the elderly and cases with severe COVID-19 infection. Both types are commonly self-limited (44, 45).

Purpuric “Vasculitic” Pattern

This cutaneous symptom is commonly due to vasculitic alterations induced by direct endothelial lesions or exacerbated inflammatory reactions. They are sometimes accompanied by necrotic lesions and can be found diffusely in the intertriginous regions or localized peripherally. The same lesions are in the form of polyarteritis nodosa related to hepatitis B

infection. Kawasaki-like eruptions resulted from COVID-19 in children seem to have a vascular origin, which can be misdiagnosed as dengue virus-induced eruptions in endemic areas. Collectively, viral hemorrhagic fevers should always be considered in the differential diagnoses. Mild cases can be managed with topical glucocorticoids, while more severe cases require systemic corticosteroids. Although not classified, ischemic and ecchymotic acral lesions have been shown in almost 10% of the cases, especially in those with severe COVID-19 infection due to hypercoagulation and disseminated intravascular coagulation. COVID-19-related acral lesions have been found on the extremities' digital, dorsal, and ventral surfaces and the heels and wrists (42, 45).

Ophthalmological Manifestations of COVID-19

Follicular Conjunctivitis

Conjunctivitis is the most prevalent ophthalmic symptom found in COVID-19 cases. In a large series of cases with mild COVID-19 infection, it has been shown that 11/127 (8.66%) cases had conjunctivitis. All symptomatic cases gave a history of redness of one or both eyes. Presence of respiratory tract manifestations were correlated with conjunctival congestion. A positive history of hand-eye contact was found in four cases; however, this did not attain clinical importance as a risk factor (46-48). This was different from the findings of a cross-sectional investigation carried out on 535 patients with COVID-19 which revealed that hand-eye contact was independently associated with the presence of conjunctival congestion amongst cases. It has been proposed that ocular symptoms are more prevalent in the middle phase of the disease based on their results of bilateral acute follicular conjunctivitis in a case on the 13th day of the illness. Delayed initiation of follicular conjunctivitis one month after severe COVID-19 infection in a 65-year-old male with diabetes, hypertension, and asthma. The conjunctival swab did not show any bacterial or fungal infection. The conjunctivitis ameliorated in 14 days with lubricants and preservative-free moxifloxacin eye drops. The investigators also reported that virus shedding in the conjunctiva may persist even after the nasopharyngeal swab becomes negative for SAR-CoV virus (46-48).

Viral Keratoconjunctivitis

Keratoconjunctivitis as the primary symptom in a case with mild respiratory manifestations has been shown. The patient showed redness, discharge, and photophobia and was managed as herpetic keratoconjunctivitis, and later, as epidemic keratoconjunctivitis with oral valacyclovir and topical moxifloxacin. SARS-CoV-2 assessment was performed only in view of updated

recommendations for evaluating cases with travel history in Canada. The nasopharyngeal and conjunctival swabs both turned out to be positive. This case shows the significance of considering conjunctivitis as a presenting manifestation of COVID-19. In another study, a case with moderate-severe COVID-19 infection with left eye conjunctivitis developing ten days after COVID-19 manifestations. At the onset of the disease, the cornea was clear, and the case had viscous discharge (46, 47). Conjunctival swab was positive for SARS-CoV-2 virus ribonucleic acid (RNA) by RT-PCR but not for herpes simplex virus (HSV) or adenovirus and this was repeated daily. On the second day of administration of topical levofloxacin and sodium hyaluronate, the swab became negative. The case recovered well within a seven days but presented with a relapse and peripheral corneal staining in both eyes after five days. This time the conjunctival swab was negative for both SARS-CoV-2 and HSV. However, the concentrations of IL-6 revealed ten-fold increase in the left eye. With an immune-mediated pathogenesis in mind, topical fluoromethalone was initiated and the case responded well with complete resolution. Since SAR-CoV-2 virus was identified in the conjunctiva, the first episode of conjunctivitis was related to local invasion and inflammation of the ocular surface resulted from the virus. It was localized to the left eye with resolution within a week. The relapse, with more widespread bilateral symptom, on the other hand, was assumed to be due to a cytokine surge resulted from an autoimmune mechanism induced by the virus. A longer follow-up with appropriate use of topical glucocorticoid is suggested by some to decrease the risk of immune-mediated keratoconjunctivitis (46-48).

Hemorrhagic and Pseudomembranous Conjunctivitis

In a study from France, a case of a 63-year-old male patient with severe COVID-19 infection was reported to be admitted in intensive care unit (ICU), developing hemorrhagic and pseudomembranous conjunctivitis 19 days after the initiation of systemic manifestations. Management was with azithromycin and dexamethasone drops and daily debridement of pseudomembrane (46-48).

Episcleritis

A case of episcleritis as the first symptom of COVID-19 has been reported in a 29-year old male. This case reported a history of foreign body sensation in the left eye and evaluation showed nasal conjunctival and episcleral congestion with blanching with phenylephrine. He showed mild viral infection with manifestations appearing three days after the ocular signs. Another investigation presented infectious symptoms of COVID-19 another case of episcleritis

which developed one week after the initiation of manifestations of COVID-19 infection. Most patients with episcleritis are idiopathic and self-limiting. About a third of them may be related to viral infections including ebola, HSV and hepatitis C and now possibly, SARS-CoV-2 virus (46-48).

Oral Manifestations of COVID-19

Oral Manifestations

The usual manifestations that cases report to the dental office even at the presymptomatic phase are ageusia (loss of taste), non-specific anosmia (loss of smell—not related to rhinitis), and hyposalivation. Few studies reported that along with unexplained ulcers in the oral cavity, desquamative gingivitis, herpetiform ulcers on attached gingiva, blisters/irregular ulcers on the tongue's dorsal surface, increase the size of submandibular glands, and cervical lymph node enlargement. These oral symptoms may be correlated with an erythematous rash on the face or viral enanthema. Dysgeusia or ageusia and anosmia is shown to be prevalent in COVID-19 cases. These manifestations are more prevalent in young cases and females, and these manifestations commonly get resolved in 03 weeks. Previous studies show that ACE2 is the receptor on target cells for the SARS-CoV-2 virus. It facilitates binding of the SARS-CoV-2 virus spike protein to the cells and subsequent infection (49). Ageusia or loss of taste is related to the presence of ACE2 expressing cells in higher numbers in the epithelial cells of the oral tissues and nasal mucosa. ACE2 expression is more critical in gustatory receptors of the tongue than the buccal or gingival tissues resulting in certain chemosensory alterations that cause ageusia. These alterations can occur due to the direct injuries to the gustatory and olfactory receptors by the SAR-CoV-2 virus. The exact mechanisms of appearance of ulcers/blisters is still unknown, and there is a wide difference in opinion of different researchers. Some authors propose these as the direct consequence of the SARS-CoV-2 infection, but most of the investigators regarded them as aphthous ulcers caused by mental stress or reactivation or new infection by different pathogen including herpes simplex virus or other opportunistic infections due to change in the immunity condition of the individual related to SARS-CoV-2 virus. The management of COVID-19 includes a combination of treatments and experimental medications. Because of these intensive drug treatments, cases may have different side effects and state several oral complaints, including pathologies of the oral mucosa, changes in salivary gland activity as well as neurological side effects (50, 51). Out of the different new treatments, antiviral medications may result in certain side-effects affecting the oral cavity, such as,

stomatitis, oral ulcers, and dry mouth. It has been shown that Interferon (IFN) α/β , used for their antiviral functions, decreases the severity of COVID-19 disease, potentially increasing survival rate, by reducing the manifestations of severe respiratory illness such as COVID-19 related pneumonia and support improvements in lung activity. Common oral side effects associated with the use of IFN- α/β may comprise dry mouth, causing common oral thrush cases. SARS-CoV-2 can also make a cytokine storm, which can aggravate existing autoimmune status in the oropharyngeal area, resulting in oral manifestations. These oral manifestations can be associated with the lack of appropriate oral care and oral evaluation in a hospital set up as the priority is to save lives during this pandemic. Besides all the above-mentioned factors, the oral ulcers can also be related to the vasculitis resulted by the excess accumulation of angiotensin II in the vascular cells. Higher accumulation of angiotensin II may lead to vasoconstriction, vascular abnormalities, and enhanced vascular permeability resulting in ulcer formation (49-51).

Dental Practice during COVID-19 Pandemic

Initially, COVID-19 pandemic caused the complete closure of almost all dental interventions throughout the world except for treatment of dental emergencies, which are potentially life-threatening due to airway obstruction, continuous tissue bleeding, trauma, facial bone fractures, and severe pain untreatable by drugs alone. With the ease in lockdown, dental interventions across the countries are opening up but with many differences in the way the treatment proceeds. These alterations are especially crucial as the infection commonly spreads through respiratory droplets or fomites and a very high viral load is identified in the oral and nasal cavity of the infected cases (49, 50). The virus has been shown in saliva in the early phases of COVID-19 cases. The dental surgeons/health care practitioner must be aware of this as they are at an increased risk of getting infected. Furthermore, the elevated viral load in respiratory droplets and saliva, the closed working environment and use of different methods like high and low-speed turbines, ultrasonic scalers/ piezoelectric instruments, 3-way syringes, dental intraoral X-rays, etc., also put the dental practitioner and health care staff at higher risk of getting infected. Not only the saliva, different oral secretions, and blood may aerosolize because of inadvertent coughing by the cases or during the interventions causing cross-contamination. Therefore, the aerosols may persist in the clinic environment for approximately 30 hours, makes an additional infection source. It should be noted that the incubation time for COVID-19 after the exposure to SARS-CoV-2 is two weeks, with cases developing COVID-19 disease 4–5 days after being infected. This data is important as even

the asymptomatic and paucisymptomatic cases can act as carriers of SARS-CoV-2 and can accelerate transmission of infection. In a recent study, it has been shown that cases in the recovery phase also can be the potential sources of virus transmission (49, 50).

ENT Manifestations of COVID-19

The nasal, nasopharyngeal and/or the oropharyngeal tissue is one of the important harbor areas of the infection, main site of taking the sample for evaluation and an important source of transmission of infection (52, 53). However, most published COVID-19 papers are focused on the lower respiratory tract symptoms and sequels due to their life-threatening nature. While, the evidence on ENT symptoms during COVID-19 infection is still sparse, thus, it is crucial to investigate ENT symptoms of such novel virus and there is a need to detect the defining ENT epidemiological and clinical features with more precision. The findings of the current investigation agree with previous studies that fever, and cough are the dominant manifestations of COVID-19 whereas gastrointestinal and ENT manifestations were infrequent, suggesting the difference in viral tropism as compared with influenza, SARS-CoV, and MERS-CoV (54). The most prevalent ENT symptoms for COVID-19 in the current investigation were sore throat (11.3%) and headache (10.7%). However, it is well known that their incidence is much less than the incidence of fever and cough in COVID-19 cases. On the other hands, nasal congestion (4.1%) and pharyngeal erythema (5.3%) were shown to occur in nearly similar incidence to the occurrence of diarrhea in those cases (4.2%). While, runny nose or rhinorrhea was shown in only 2.1% of COVID-19 cases. Therefore, if we choose one ENT symptom to be added to the criteria of diagnosis of suspected subjects or the triage check list for covid-19, we will choose the sore throat and not the runny nose. While sore throat was reported in COVID-19 cases in higher incidence than diarrhea that is included in some triage checklists for COVID-19, so this requires to be revised (54). All the stated ENT symptoms in COVID-19 cases are nonspecific and so could be easily missed and no emergency ENT manifestations as bleeding per nose or throat or stridor was published in COVID-19 patients. No ear or laryngeal symptoms were reported. No documented sneezing, epistaxis, or post nasal discharge so the role of the nose in disease transmission is thought to be much less than cough. Post viral anosmia is one of the chief causes of smell dysfunction in adults. Viruses that give rise to the common cold or upper respiratory tract infections are well characterized to make post-infectious smell loss. The previously reported coronaviruses seem to account for 10-15% patients (53). So, the novel COVID-19 virus proposed also to be able to make anosmia in infected cases and if it occurs, it will not be a specific outcome. Smell and taste impairments in COVID-19 cases were sparsely

reported in the literature and there is still a paucity of peer-reviewed literature to approve a causal correlation between anosmia and COVID-19. Furthermore, most investigations on smell in COVID-19 cases did not fully show the clinical symptoms of the cases so we could not include in the current book. In a non-peer reviewed published study; it has been shown that loss of smell and taste were found in 59% of COVID-19 positive cases compared to 18% of those with COVID-19 negative test. They proposed that a combination of loss of smell and taste, fever, persistent cough, fatigue, GIT manifestations is a predictive of COVID-19 positive test with good specificity and average sensitivity. But they don't state whether anosmia was developed prior to other COVID-19 manifestations, during the disease or afterwards (52-54).

Pharmacological and Dietary Interventions for Management of COVID-19

Dietary Supplementation

All published papers stated that there are currently no known supplements to prevent COVID-19. Only 2 evidence reported that it might be possible to use supplements to meet dietary suggestions. Some vitamins and minerals increase immunity; however, the idea that more is better is a misconception. Megadoses of vitamins and minerals can cause toxic and adverse effects or interact with treatments, causing increased or decreased pharmacological roles. On the other hand, it is crucial to consider that Dietary Reference Intakes have been approved for healthy subjects and are based on a diet providing 2000 kcal/d. Therefore, healthcare professionals should individualize dietary programs by considering variables that can increase nutrient needs, such as specific diseases/conditions, treatments, dietary patterns, and exercise intensity (55, 56). For this reason, the range from the Recommended Dietary Allowance to the Tolerable Upper Intake Level can be applied to optimize the dietary program. The Brazilian Association of Clinical Nutrition suggested that vitamin C supplementation may be effective for cases at risk of respiratory viral infections. Vitamin C is a well-known antioxidant nutrient that can increase chemotaxis, phagocytosis, production of reactive oxygen species, and, ultimately, microbial killing. However, a systematic review including 10 708 subjects revealed that doses of vitamin C exceeding 1 g/d were not effective in decreasing the incidence of colds among the overall population. On the other hand, such doses may be beneficial in decreasing the duration of colds by 8% to 18%. Moreover, vitamin C may be effective to prevent the initiation of colds in cases exposed to brief periods of intense physical activity or to cold temperatures (56, 57). Vitamin D is another antioxidant that has been correlated with a decrease in pulmonary infections. Results of the studies that vitamin D can prevent or treat influenza are

inconclusive, but vitamin D level has been correlated with the severity of COVID-19. Potential pathways include enhanced secretion of antimicrobial peptides, reduced synthesis of chemokines, suppression of dendritic cell activation, and changed T-cell activation (56, 57).

None of the studies stated here recommended vitamin D supplementation as preventive treatment against COVID-19. However, one study proposed that regions south of latitude 35 north have low population mortality, which may suggest a role of vitamin D in indicating outcomes from COVID-19. When deficiency is identified, oral supplementation with doses between 2000 and 4000 IU/d is indicated. Although a higher dose has been recently suggested with the aim of decreasing the risk of infection this is still inconclusive and contradicts other suggestions. Since it is not feasible to suggest biochemical analysis of vitamin D concentrations during a pandemic, targeting vulnerable cases for vitamin D supplementation can mitigate the health risks correlated with COVID-19, especially since vitamin D deficiency has been proposed to associate with hypertension, diabetes mellitus, obesity, and darker skin pigmentation (56). Although it may be conflicting, vitamin D supplementation to prevent deficiency may, at the very least, provide effects by sustaining bone mass during lockdown. Zinc and selenium are antioxidant micronutrients often suggested for supplementation. Zinc is a cofactor of superoxide dismutase, an enzyme present in the mitochondria and cytosol of cells that prevents oxidative stress. Excess zinc, however, also makes cellular oxidative stress. A narrative review revealed clear evidence of the antiviral function of zinc against a variety of viruses, such as influenza. Furthermore, zinc is crucial in development of both innate and acquired (humoral) antiviral activities. However, the investigators suggested that more investigations are required on the antiviral pathways and clinical effects of zinc supplementation as a preventative and therapeutic intervention for viral infections (56, 58). A recent investigation proposed that the elderly are at risk for zinc deficiency, which increases susceptibility to infections such as pneumonia. Zinc supplementation may be appropriate for improvement of immune function and to decrease the risk of infections in this group. Selenium has been shown to enhance the function of glutathione peroxidase, another antioxidant enzyme, and to augment a number of host immune mechanisms, including interferon c synthesis, T-cell generation, antigen stimulation, and natural killer cell function. In fact, an experimental investigation with mice and influenza virus revealed that selenium deficiency resulted in more severe disease and an elevated proinflammatory immune response, causing increased pathology in the lungs (56, 58, 59). Selenium is a critical trace element that can be identified in nuts, breads, grains, meat, poultry, fish, and eggs and is easily obtainable from dietary

sources. Taken together, it is preferable to receive antioxidants from food rather than from supplements. However, supplements are suggested for cases who have specific challenges in meeting dietary needs. The key message about dietary supplements is that cases should not rely on supplements to prevent COVID-19. More investigations on the effects of vitamin and mineral supplementation on outcomes associated with COVID-19 are warranted. Nowadays, several studies on vitamin D, vitamin C, zinc, and selenium supplementation are under way. It is hoped that the findings of these investigations will result in a better understanding of the association between micronutrients and COVID-19 (58, 59).

Summary of Pharmacological Interventions

Since the outbreak and subsequent declaration of COVID-19 as a global pandemic in March 2020, concerted investigations have been carried out by the scientific community to prevent the spread of the disease and suggest an effective cure. While vaccines constitute a vital part of the public health method to decrease the burden of COVID-19, the treatment of this disease will continue to depend on heavily on pharmacotherapy. This book aims to provide an updated review of pharmacological medications that have been developed and/or repurposed for the management of COVID-19 (60, 61). To this end, a comprehensive literature assessment was performed using different databases including the PubMed, Google Scholar, and LitCovid databases. Relevant clinical investigations on medications used in the treatment of COVID-19 were detected and assessed in terms of evidence of efficacy and safety. To date, the FDA has validated three treatments for the management of COVID-19 Emergency Use Authorization: convalescent plasma, remdesivir, and casirivimab/imdevimab (REGN-COV2). Medications such as lopinavir/ritonavir, umifenovir, favipiravir, anakinra, chloroquine, hydroxychloroquine, tocilizumab, interferons, tissue plasminogen activator, intravenous immunoglobulins, and nafamosat have been applied off-label with mixed therapeutic findings (60, 61). Adjunctive use of corticosteroids is also very frequent. The clinical experience with these approved and repurposed medications is limited, and evidence on efficacy for the new indication are not promising. Taken together, the response of the global scientific community to the COVID-19 pandemic has been interesting, as evident from the volume of scientific literature showing the molecular biology and pathophysiology of SARS-CoV-2 and the establishment of three new medications for clinical treatment. Reviewed investigations have revealed inconsistent findings on efficacy and safety of the currently utilized medications. The lack of standard management for COVID-19 has made it difficult to interpret findings from most of the published investigations due to the risk of attribution error. The long-term role of

medications can only be evaluated after several years of clinical experience; therefore, the efficacy and safety of current COVID-19 treatments should continue to be strictly assessed as part of post-marketing investigations (55, 60).

Conclusion

Diagnosis of different manifestations of COVID-19 could be crucial as this could help clinicians and researchers better understand the virulence, pathology, and immune responses associated with SARS-CoV-2, and also early diagnosis of the disease in suspected cases leading to the development of effective therapies and treatment plans. In this review, we showed the different effects of COVID-19, thus emphasizing that the disease can present in various manifestations and the healthcare providers need to be extra vigilant, approaching all cases with a high index of suspicion.

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